

Research, Development and Enhancement of High-performance Polymer Matrix Composites for Aerospace in China

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ABSTRACT

Research and development at LAC/BIAM has focused on polymer matrix composite system possessing excellent damage resistance and processing ease for aerospace industry. The goal has been achieved by development of an innovative toughening technology platform, so-called *Ex-situ* concept, both for prepreg-autoclave and liquid molding technique like RTM and RFI. High-performance epoxy, bismaleimide and polyimide matrix composites have been developed by using the LAC/BIAM's proprietary concept. Processing conditions and mechanical properties of the trial products have been demonstrated. Particularly the interlaminar toughness and impact damage resistance and tolerance have been significantly improved, with balanced in-plane properties even at hot/wet conditions and good processabilities.

KEYWORDS: Toughening, epoxy, bismaleimide, polyimide, RTM

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber polymer matrix composites are currently the standard structural materials for commercial airplane applications. Most prominent is the potential for weight savings, together with potential for improved fatigue behavior. Although the fibrous phase provides most of the strength and stiffness requirements, many key composite properties are matrix dominated. The interaction between the polymer phases in the matrix and particularly the multiple-structural architecture of the commonly laminated composite system determines the overall performance.

Due to the importance of the matrices and particularly the interlaminar morphology and microstructure in contributing to the overall composite performance, works at LAC/BIAM have been concerned with the development, modification and enhancement of matrices in conjunction with the interlaminar microstructure having capabilities competitive to the current commercial systems [1]. Significant efforts have been devoted to the interlaminar toughening concepts offering scope for carbon fiber laminated composites. As a successful result, LAC/BIAM developed and demonstrated an innovative toughening concept, so-called *Ex-situ* concept [2]. Based on the concept, the R & D ranges from standard aerospace-grade epoxy, high-temperature cured bismaleimide, to MDA-free polyimide and the RTMable polyimide, all of these composites are additionally toughened. The trial products can be categorized to the third generation of toughened composite materials for aerospace applications. An overview and product portfolio will be presented. All products with "E" or "ES" suffix in the presentation means that they are toughened by using *Ex-situ* concept. An understanding of the complicated multiple structural details and the toughening mechanism are necessary to use the concept to laminated composites with different resin chemistry.

2. TOUGHENED EPOXY PREPREG SYSTEM

The nature of the matrix phase, in particular its inherent toughness, has been recognized as offering a contribution to composite toughness. For many resins considered for airplane applications, thermoplastic modification leading to so-called thermoset/thermoplastic two-phase system has been seen as the preferred toughening technique. The toughening is based on the crosslinking reaction induced phase separation and coarsening mechanism [3, 4, 5]. The composition and the process control play a central roll in establishment of the particular morphology and microstructure.

As reported recently [6], the material being used on the 787's primary structures, such as the wings and fuselage, is a redevelopment of the Toray Composites America Toray 3900-2 prepreg material (comprised of intermediate-modulus T800 carbon fiber and a toughened 177°C-cure

epoxy) used on the 777. The new version, used in both a unidirectional tape and woven formats, has equal design and component manufacturing performance as the original material specified for the 777. But Toray has changed the method for adding the thermoplastic toughening agent to reduce its cost, and the more recent material product form is in production use on the 777 on a substitution basis. Similar commercially available tow-phase toughened epoxies with higher hot/wet service temperatures include IM7/977-2 supplied by Cytec ENGINEERED MATERIALS. For instance, Cycom® 977-2A is a 177°C-curing, toughened resin with a 126-138°C dry and 104°C wet service capability [7].

5228, an own development at LAC/BIAM, is a 180°C cure, toughened epoxy resin with a 130°C dry and 110°C wet service capability (Table 1). The T300 carbon fiber reinforced unidirectional laminated composites 5228E/T300 using the resin and modified with LAC/BIAM' proprietary *Ex-situ* toughening concept indicates higher impact damage resistance and tolerance, excellent hot/wet mechanical properties with manufacturing ease (Table 2). 5228E is formulated for autoclave or press molding. Typical applications for 5228E include aircraft primary and secondary structure, space structure, ballistics, cryogenic tanks, or any application where impact resistance and light weight are required.

Table 1 Typical technical data of 5228 resin

Tensile strength	MPa	98
Tensile modulus	GPa	3.5
Elongation at break	%	4.3
Flexural strength	MPa	148
Flexural modulus	GPa	3.4
Tg (DMTA, tan(delta))	°C	220

Table 2 Typical technical data of 5228E/T300(UD) composite

0° Tensile strength	MPa	2550
0° Tensile modulus	GPa	147
90° Tensile strength	MPa	75.9
90° Tensile modulus	GPa	8.62
90° Elongation at break	%	0.99
0° Compression strength	MPa	1300
0° Compression modulus	GPa	121
Flexural strength	MPa	1900
Flexural modulus	GPa	132
Interlaminar shear strength	MPa	95
130°C Wet flexural strength ^a	MPa	1140
130°C Wet flexural modulus ^a	GPa	107
130°C Wet interlaminar shear strength ^a	MPa	42.3
Open Hole compression strength	MPa	275
Open Hole tensile strength	MPa	485
G _{IC}	J/m ²	513
G _{IIC}	J/m ²	622
G _C edge delamination toughness	J/m ²	382
Compression after impact (4.45Jmm ⁻¹)	MPa	289

Note a: in boiled water (95-100°C) for 48h.

It is interesting to study the unique interlaminar morphology for 5228E sample [8, 9]. It is, at the first look (Figure 1), nothing new except for the phase-decomposed and -inversed granular structure usually observed for the reaction induced decomposition reaction [3,4,5]: the epoxy-rich particles are "coated" by continuous thermoplastic (PAEK) thin films, which were previously chemically etched away for the SEM study. Furthermore, the granular structure was slightly penetrated into the graphite plies, establishing an inter-anchored boundary between the co-continuous granular structure and graphite ply impregnated with the pure epoxy. Because of the inter-anchoring effect, crack propagation resistant was significantly with a complicated fiber pull-out process (Figure 2). The PAEK is a thermoplastic toughening component developed in China.

(a) Phase-inversed granular morphology of a cast 5228E as bulk cast and in the laminate. (b) Interlaminar morphology of *Ex-situ* sample. In both cases, the thermoplastic continuous phase (PAEK) was chemically etched away.

Fig 2. Representative of fiber pull-out after G_{IC} test

To establish and control the characteristic interlaminar morphology (Fig. 1a), TTT diagram (Temperature-Time-Transformation) was constructed for 5228E from the contours of the logarithmic time to gel and to vitrify as a function of the reaction temperature shown in Figure 3a [10]. Basically, the diagram is based on the gelation model and vitrification model, respectively. It shows the relationship between the characteristic temperatures including T_{g0} , T_{ggel} and $T_{g\infty}$, behind them there is the polymeric structure established, and the processing conditions in dependence of temperature and time. The characteristic *Ex-situ* interlaminar morphology can only be produced if the interfacial diffusion, the curing reaction, the reaction-induced phase separation and the resin impregnation process are well understood as a competitive process and optimum controlled [11]. For example, the traditional cure process of 130°C/0.5h+180°C/2h+200°C/2h was altered to 130°C/1h+180°C/2h+200°C/2h (Figure 3b) in order to control the diffusion depth of the low-molecular epoxy component into the thermoplastic PAEK. The morphological investigation reveals that the control was successful. As shown in Figure 4, a phase separated and inverted co-continuous morphology was set up with the controlled diffusion depth [12].

(a) TTT diagram of 5228E

(b) Comparison of the optimized and traditional cure cycle

Fig. 3 TTT diagram and the cure cycles for 5228E

Fig. 4 Phase morphology of laminated resin model at different cure cycles corresponding to Fig. 3b

Most notable amongst the *Ex-situ* technology has been published elsewhere [i.e. 13].

3. TOUGHENED RTMABLE BISMALIMIDE SYSTEM

BMI's are technically a type of polyimide, prepared from the reaction of maleic anhydride and a diamine. BMI's bridge the temperature performance gap between epoxies and the polyimides. They exhibit epoxy-like processing characteristics, curing by an addition polymerization, rather than a condensation reaction. Thus, they avoid the off-gassing characteristic of polyimides and have temperature performance intermediate between epoxy and polyimide. Brittleness also is an issue with traditional BMI's used in airframes, and resin suppliers are working to address this with thermoplastic or elastomeric fillers.

As example, Hexcel's F655 resin is one BMI product that sacrifices a bit of temperature performance for enhanced toughness. F655's T_g in dry conditions is 288°C, and it exhibits excellent compression strength after impact. In addition to standard autoclave processing, Hexcel's BMI also can be processed via RTM methods. F655 resin is being used by The Nordam Group for the Gulfstream G-450 thrust reverser. Cytec Engineered Materials Inc. is well known for its BMI resin products used in aerospace, as well as its extensive overall high-temperature materials portfolio. Cycom-5250-4 is Cytec's best-known BMI product. The resin has a dry T_g of 296°C, and RTM' parts exhibit continuous service temperature resistance up to 204°C, with excellent toughness. Cytec's BMI resins have been used for years in F-22 fighter jet parts [14].

LAC/BIAM's 6421 is the well-known all-purpose BMI product in China, which can be prepregged or used as an RTM resin. 6421 resin exhibits good flow behavior for RTM, and its RTM processing window including the curing is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 The viscosity curve of 6421 resin and the curing cycle of 6421 composites

When *Ex-situ* toughened [15], 6421ES/G827-T700 composites possess excellent toughness. The interlaminar fracture toughness showed significant increase from 215 to 627 J/m² in G_{IC} and from 510 to 905 J/m² in G_{IIC} , respectively [16]. The increases in interlaminar fracture toughness are found to attribute to the relief of plastic constraint at the crack tip by thermoplastic-rich phases in the BMI matrix composites. Fractographic evidence of the plastic deformation and rupture along the crack paths is presented for both Mode I and Mode II tests.

Meanwhile, the CAI exhibits also significant increase from 155 to about 277 MPa [17]. The crack propagation was deflected or bifurcated by BMI particles or stopped by tearing of the thermoplastic component phase, which resulted in the improvement in delamination resistance of the composites. The energy absorption mechanism was changed from the delamination to fiber fracture, which contributed to the significant improvement in CAI. Figure 6 exhibits additionally for the composites reinforced with China-made T300-grade carbon fiber fabric G827 (denoted as CG827) the compression strength after impact (σ_{CAI} , or CAI), the failure strain (ϵ_{CAI}) and the indentation depth (d) in dependence of the impact energy (IE). It is apparent that both the σ_{CAI} and ϵ_{CAI} decrease with the impact energy while the indentation depth increases.

Figure 6. Plot of the Impact damage residual strength, failure strain and indentation depth of 6421ES/CG827-T300 laminates against the impact energy

6421ES/G827's T_g in untoughened dry conditions is about 295°C. Downside is the insufficient hot/wet properties limited by the thermoplastic toughening agent, the T_g decreases in *Ex-situ* toughened condition to about 220°C. The RTM's parts exhibit continuous service temperature resistance up to 170°C. Typical mechanical data for the test conditions are presented in Table 3 for both non-toughened (control) and *Ex-situ* toughened specimens for comparison. The ongoing project is to increase the glass transition temperature at the hot/wet conditions and to maximize the performance potential of the material.

Table 3. 0° tensile modulus (a) and strength (b), 0° compression modulus (c) and strength (d), longitudinal transverse shear modulus (e) and strength (f), flexural strength and modulus (h), interlaminar shear strength (i), open hole tensile (j) and compression strength (k) of G827/6421ES composite non-toughened (control) in comparison to those *Ex-situ* toughened.

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

Intensive research results and expanded technical data of the 6421ES/G827 composites are available, also those of 6421ES prepreg system [18].

4. TOUGHENED POLYIMIDE PREPREG AND RTM SYSTEMS

Traditional linear polyimides have a high melt viscosity that limits processability and,

consequently, end-use. By lowering the molecular weight and using reactive end-capping agents to produce thermosetting polyimides, the processability has been improved. Thermosetting polyimides, originally developed in the 1970s at NASA Lewis for military aircraft engines and airframes, are produced by dissolving an aromatic diamine, a dialkyl ester of tetracarboxylic acid and a monofunctional nadic ester end-capping agent in a solvent, such as alcohol. The resulting solution is typically used to produce prepreg. PMR-15 is the best known of these thermosetting formulations. PMR is shorthand for in-situ polymerization of monomer reactants [14]. Typical equivalent products in China include KH-304. It has successfully been used in many aerospace applications.

But, while PMR-15 and similar variants have good mechanical properties, they contain the hazardous compound methylenedianiline (MDA), creating a potential health and safety issue. RP-46, patented in 1991, is a direct PMR-15 replacement with very similar chemistry. Unitech Corp. is one of two licensees of the RP-46 resin technology. An equivalent trial product in China to RP-46 is LP-15, developed at LAC/BIAM.

Because of its high degree of crosslinking, the carbon fiber reinforced LP-15 composite has a glass transition temperature (T_g) of 335°C and sustained service temperature of 288°C. LP-15's thermoxidative stability is high, meaning it resists oxidation (combustion) that breaks down molecular bonds and causes weight loss and structural decline, even at high temperature. Tensile and flexural strength is 520MPa at 300°C under hot/wet conditions (Table 4). Usually the high crosslink densities also make polyimides fairly brittle, and microcracking under repeated heat cycles can occur, although in many applications, it isn't an issue. Thanks to the *Ex-situ* technique applied to carbon fiber composites, the composite material of LP15ES/AS4 exhibits high toughness [19]. The microcracking tendency is significantly reduced whereas the impact damage resistance characterized with CAI is increased from non-toughened 200MPa to toughened 327MPa (Table 4).

Table 4. High temperature properties of LP15ES/AS4 composite

	RT	500°F (260°C)	536°F (280°C)	572°F (300°C)
Tensile strength (MPa)	1850	1790	1650	520
Tensile modulus (GPa)	140	138	136	125
Flexural strength (MPa)	1950	1650	1050	520
Flexural modulus (GPa)	134	131	128	83
ILSS (MPa)	87	85	58	46
CAI (MPa)	327	-	-	-
Fiber volume fraction: $V_f = 58-64\%$				

As reported [20-22], NASA's focus was on different polyimide chemistry, termed phenylethynyl (PE), or sometimes referred to as PETI, for phenylethynyl terminated imide, a reference to the polymer chain's phenylethynyl end caps. PETI resins came about because of the desire for a structural matrix resin that could provide higher temperature performance and longer-term thermoxidative stability than bismaleimides. Since the resin cures in an addition reaction without volatile evolution, void and microcrack-free carbon/PETI demonstration parts have been produced with T_g s as high as 330°C and continuous use temperatures (>1000 hours) of 288°C, using a material identified as PETI-330. M & P Technologies Inc. has used PETI-330 to produce complex parts with RTM, and flat laminates have been made with vacuum-assisted RTM (VARTM). While PETI-330 is readily commercialized by UBE America, still in development is its next version PETI-375, with T_g s as high as 375°C. While these resins, designed for primary structural applications in airframes and jet engines, produce tough composites, they do cost more than PMR-type materials.

As part of an ongoing effort to develop materials for resin transfer molding (RTM), and in a close cooperation¹ with Changchun Institute of Applied Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences,

¹ 973 Consortium (2003CB615604)

and Jilin University, Changchun, a new phenylethynyl containing imide designated as 9731 has firstly been prepared and evaluated at LAC/BIAM. 9731 was synthesized using asymmetric-biphenyltetracarboxylic dianhydride (a-BPDA), balanced 3,4'-oxydianiline (3,4'-ODA) and 4,4'-oxydianiline (4,4'-ODA), and endcapped with 4-phenylethynylphthalic anhydride (4-PEPA). At a calculated number average molecular weight (M_n) of 750 g/mol, the resin exhibits a stable melt viscosity of about 0.1-0.5 Pa·sec at 280°C (Figure 7a) and cured glass transition temperatures (T_g) of about 360°C (Figure 7b). The lower melt viscosity is presumably due to the highly irregular structure of the polyimide emanating from a-BPDA. In the structure/property relationship of polyimides, it is highly unusual for a monomer to provide both an increase in T_g and a decrease in melt viscosity. Due primarily to the attributes of a-BPDA, 9731 offers improved processability and high temperature performance.

Figure 7. Viscosity profile and the TTT diagram of 9731 resin

The laminates were subsequently made with T700 carbon fiber fabric G827 on a specially constructed injection molding set-up. The original sizing was not removed. All of the laminates, both the non-toughened and *Ex-situ* toughened, were of high quality as determined by C-scan. Examination for microcracks on as-processed laminates indicated no microcracking present.

It is noteworthy that a thermoplastic polyimide toughening agent (3,4-BPDA-4,4'-ODA) with similar chemical structure has been also synthesized for the *Ex-situ* toughening. Figure 8 shows the chemical structure of both the basic polyimide resin 9731 and toughening agent.

Figure 8. the RTMable base resin and the thermoplastic modifier as toughening agent

The basic mechanical properties of non-toughened 9731/G827 and toughened 9731ES/G827 are presented in Table 5. It is apparent that the data are generally comparable with 6421/G827 composites (refer to Tab. 3). However at high temperature, e.g. at 288°C, the 9731ES composite exhibits a significantly better retention of room temperature strengths and Modulus whereas the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) retained about 45% of their room temperature strength. This was not surprising since the modulus is a fiber-dominated property.

Table 5. Basic mechanical properties of 9731ES/G827

Properties	25°C		288°C	
	Control	<i>Ex-Situ</i>	Control	<i>Ex-Situ</i>
Tensile strength (MPa)	1541	1423	1443	1312

Tensile modulus (GPa)	113	101	109	103
Flexural strength (MPa)	1726	1667	1128	1112
Flexural modulus (GPa)	119	96	113	95.9
Compress strength (MPa)	958	948	827	820
Compress modulus (GPa)	113	109	107	105
ILSS (MPa)	97.9	110	56.7	52.7
T _g (°C) by DMTA	410°C	398.9°C	---	---

The interlaminar property retention was most likely affected by the toughening agent. In order to assess the effect of composition ratio between the base polyimide and toughening agent on the glass transition temperature, DMTA (Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis) has been employed (Figure 9a). As indicated, T_g of the blends decreases slightly with the thermoplastic concentration. However, T_g can also be influenced if taking the post-curing into consideration (Figure 9b). At a post-curing temperature of 370°C, the T_g of both the base resin and the toughened blend increases. The increased crosslinking density in dependence on the post-curing duration is thought responsible for the increase in T_g.

Figure 9. Glass transition temperature in dependence of the composition (thermosetting : thermoplastic) and post-curing duration

In an attempt to expand the database on the composites, an initial assessment of composite performance was devoted to interlaminar fracture toughness and impact damage resistance. The results obtained at ambient temperature are shown in Table 6. It is obvious that both G_{IC} and G_{IIC} of the toughened specimens exhibit dramatically higher values compared to those non-toughened. This is a direct reflection of the effectiveness of *Ex-situ* concept. Correspondingly, there is a significant increase in CAI. Thus, 9731ES/G827 composite offers an unprecedented combination of processability and laminate toughness.

Table 6 Interlaminar toughness and compression after impact of 9731ES/G827 composites

Properties	Control	<i>Ex-Situ</i>
G_{IC} (J/m ²)	310	459
G_{IIC} (J/m ²)	590	1100
CAI (MPa)	137	249

Morphological investigation by means of SEM revealed that the fracture surfaces of composites toughened with *Ex-situ* RTM technique was rough, as shown in Figure 10b and c. The typical phase separated and inverted particles structure was confirmed by large magnification (Fig. 10d and e). The thermosetting polyimide-rich particles are extremely fine, surrounded by continuous thermoplastic polyimide-rich phase. Under the G_{IC} test, the crack propagation resulted in the plastic deformation of the particles from a shape of globular to elliptical. The orientation of the particles was at an angle to the fibers. The cavitations or debonding of the particles phases and

the plastic yielding of the thermosetting polyimide-rich and thermoplastic polyimide-rich phases was recognized as toughening mechanism. The deformation of the thermosetting particles and the plastic tearing of the thermoplastic phase resulted in the increase in G_{IC} .

Figure 10. Fracture surface of 9731EX/G827 composite after mode I test (a:500X, b:2000X, c:20000X, d:40000X, e:80000X)

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

R & D programs within LAC/BIAM have resulted in the development of potential composite materials covering a wide-range resin chemistries i.e. epoxy, bismaleimide and polyimide for typical processing methods, i.e. prepreg-autoclave and RTM. Specially, the innovative *Ex-situ* toughening concept has shown improved interlaminar toughness and impact damage resistance of all the composites presented.

Application of *Ex-situ* concept to an epoxy matrix prepreg composites has led to an innovative product 5228E with dramatically enhanced CAI. Most important properties of 5228E/T300(UD) composite have shown significant improvement. The result was achieved by sophisticated control of the interlaminar morphology and microstructure. The Time-Temperature Transformation diagram (TTT diagram) was employed to design and control the curing cycle.

Similarly, the *Ex-situ* concept works well for RTMable composites. A wide range of test results has demonstrated on a bismaleimide matrix composite 6421ES/G827-T700 RTM-manufactured. Particularly the G_{IC} , G_{IIC} and CAI have increased by about a factor of two, with minimal change in other important mechanical properties and with processing ease.

For application at elevated temperatures, PMR-type, MDA-free polyimide resin LP15 for autoclave and RTMable polyimide resin 9731 has been developed. The carbon laminates with both of them as matrix resin were additionally *Ex-situ* toughened, leading to trial product of LP15ES/AS4 and 9731ES/G827, respectively. The results have indicated that the composites offer an unprecedented combination of processability and laminate toughness, compared to the non-toughened one.

At LAC/BIAM, work is underway to increase the technical maturity of *Ex-situ* technology. The target composite system will potentially cover the full-range of service temperatures of composite structure used in airplanes and the full-range of processing methods like prepreg/autoclave, RTM and RFI etc.

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